

Adoption and Strategic Use of Artificial Intelligence in Public Relations: A Study of PR Practitioners in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the understanding, adoption, and strategic application of artificial intelligence (AI) in modern Public Relations (PR) practice. Data were gathered from professionals employed by government agencies, non-profits, corporations, and consulting firms using a survey design. Based on diffusion of innovation theory, the main goal was to investigate awareness, adoption trends, perceived influence, opportunities, and difficulties related to AI in public relations. The core objective was to examine levels of awareness, adoption trends, perceived impact, opportunities, and difficulties related to AI in public relations; it was anchored on diffusion of innovation theory. A structured questionnaire on AI's influence on PR operations was administered. The majority of respondents were involved in general communication (85%) and media relations (68%). Findings revealed a high prevalence of AI usage among practitioners, notably through smartphone assistants (87%) and smart devices (58%), with no significant gender differences in adoption trends. Participants largely conceptualized AI as automated, data-driven systems capable of informed decision-making. The study highlights that regular use of AI technologies does not necessarily translate into strategic application expertise. Consequently, it recommends deliberate professional development through structured training programmes, AI literacy should be taught in PR programs, and organizations such as the Nigerian Institute of Public Relations (NIPR) should take the initiative to encourage the ethical, responsible, and educated adoption of AI.

Keywords: AI awareness, professional competence, public relations, communication professionals, and artificial intelligence.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most significant changes in the evolution of communications is the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into public relations. As its main objective is to build and maintain relationships between businesses and various parties, the field of public relations (PR) has been constantly evolving due to social and technical progress (Lock, 2023). The use of AI is a revolutionary power that is transforming how PR is being conducted in this generation. One of the essential elements of changing PR activities in current communication settings, compelled mainly by technology, is AI (Pinto & Bhadra, 2024).

The current media landscape, as it is, is increasingly becoming more intertwined with PR practice, specifically in social networks, the primary avenue of communication (Çerçi, 2024). The evolution of AI in PR is closely connected to the growth of digital technology in general; the improvement of processing power, faster network systems, and massive data sets have all made it possible to develop advanced AI applications (Buhmann & White, 2022).

A thriving organization in the modern globalized world largely depends on effective communication, and PR has been at the forefront of influencing the perception of the masses, reputation management, and reaching out to a multitude (Anani-Bossman, 2021). The idea of artificial intelligence (AI) has now permeated most aspects of society, including public relations (PR), offering new tools and opportunities that are altering how PR campaigns are created, how data is seen, how messages are tailored, and how reputations are upheld (Septiana, 2025).

The use of AI in PR started to receive official attention, with the (Chartered Institute of Public Relations (CIPR), 2023) paper *Humans Still Needed 2018*, which explored what is expected to happen to the industry in five years, as the first step in this direction. Nevertheless, due to the rapid pace of AI evolution, these concepts have been expanded in subsequent studies and described as higher-quality work and faster completion of tasks, as the most current State of AI in PR survey shows. Among these professionals, 89 percent say that AI can assist them in completing assignments more quickly, and 74 percent believe that it has enhanced the quality of their work (Muck Rack, 2024).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Public Relations AI Models

The way public relations (PR) professionals understand their roles is changing significantly as a result of artificial intelligence (AI) models (Buhmann et al., 2022). Predictive analytics, machine learning, and natural language processing tools are being used more and more in public relations campaigns to improve accuracy, speed, and overall effectiveness and efficiency. AI is transforming the process of messaging, audience interpretation, and the management of

reputational issues by automating routine tasks and providing data-driven recommendations (Alaawad, 2021).

One of the AI technologies that do affect Natural language processing (NLP), which enables computer systems to read and write human language, is a PR practice. Media tracking and sentiment analysis must be done with NLP (Jim et al., 2024). Contemporary AI systems can process large volumes of online content, such as blogs, news items, and posts on social media platforms in real time and ascertain whether the idea of the brand is holding a neutral, positive, or negative opinion on the same.

The AI application in automated content development is also increasing rapidly. Press releases, blog articles, social media updates, and other content can be written by generative AI systems, which drastically cut down on writing time while maintaining message coherence and consistency (Kumar et al., 2024). Reports by the Chartered Institute of Public Relations (CIPR) show that the use of these tools is increasingly growing to create communication pieces that are audience-specific. These systems generate personalized content that is aligned with the objectives and needs of the audience as they learn about previous campaigns and customer engagement (Haleem, Javaid, Qadri, Singh, & Suman, 2022).

The other important PR strategy is the AI-powered predictive analytics that utilizes both past and present data to guide professionals to predict the outcomes of communication (Madupati, 2022). These models facilitate decisions on what the audience should do, how the message should be framed, and when the campaign should be conducted. Other technologies, such as predictive technologies, can tell when it is time to make a statement or what type of content will receive the most interactions. Surveys show that more than 65% of PR professionals have seen their workflow become more efficient and successful when predictive analytics are integrated into it (Muck Rack, 2024).

By identifying the most likely journalists, influencers, or media outlets to interact with a specific story, AI-driven recommendation systems also help with media relations. These algorithms consider the demographics of the audience, the interests of the journalist, and the trends of the past publications to draw proper recommendations. This enhances the PR and enhances the chances of pitching success (Mardhika, 2023). Moreover, virtual assistants and chatbots powered by AI are increasingly being used to manage the participation of the audience in real time.

With that said, AI models can be your helping hand in a large variety of PR activities, such as media targeting, sentiment analysis, content production, and predictive forecasting. Human creativity, moral judgment, and emotional intelligence will never be as insignificant, although AI will enable practitioners to

devote more of their attention to relationship building and strategic planning. The AI in Communications Industry Opportunities and Risks research states that AI is a supplement, and it adds to human experience in the dynamic industry of public relations, but does not replace it (Sandpiper and PROvoke, 2024).

The PR Advantages of Artificial Intelligence Technologies

The growing usage of artificial intelligence (AI) is causing a paradigm shift in many different professional fields, including public relations (PR). Even though artificial intelligence (AI) has been around for decades, its widespread usage in public relations is still a relatively new and rapidly developing issue. Recent developments suggest that AI can have a substantial effect on enhancing PR strategies and success (Kalogiannidis et al., 2024). Nevertheless, the lack of research on the impact of AI on PR makes it an even more significant concern, with the rising prominence of the technology also introducing serious concerns in terms of ethical, technical, or operational risks. Such research is necessary. The emergence of the digital era has given rise to massive data-generating speed, variety, and volume, leading to the adoption of AI-based systems in organizations (Joshi, 2025). The application of AI to CRM provides PR professionals with an excellent instrument to optimise client interactions and facilitate communication with the client since effective CRM lies in the integration of marketing strategies, technological advances, available data, and organizational frameworks (Turksoy, 2022).

The ability of AI to significantly reduce the time and amount of operating costs is one of the main advantages of using it to analyze large amounts of data to help with CRM. The ability of AI to work with large datasets fast and efficiently helps organizations to save money and human resources and make well-informed decisions in time (Enholt, Papagiannidis, Mikalef, & Krogstie, 2022). The AI systems have enhanced their abilities due to the enhanced data management, retrieval, and storage that is achievable via the increased use of cloud-based technologies (Palos-Sánchez, Baena-Luna, Badicu, & Infante-Moro, 2022).

It is now necessary to use AI in media monitoring, which is one of the main responsibilities of PR, along with CRM. AI-powered platforms can all support real-time sentiment analysis, digital interaction analysis, and media conversation tracking. With such insights, PR teams have an opportunity to produce strong and targeted content to share on social media since they get to know their current and potential audiences.

PR practitioners are being pressured to act fast and to be active on social platforms. AI-based monitoring systems reduce this load and provide full-time engagement to the audience, and generate valuable insights. These systems can determine the right format, tone, and time of responses. However, the modern

AI-based technologies are not yet able to make fully autonomous decisions and act within the limits of pre-established algorithms (Merhi, 2023).

Monitoring technologies based on AI replace repetitive interaction tasks with automation and rapidly use user posts, comments, and replies to classify them. Before the advent of AI, PR employees were able to do all of this manually, which was labor-intensive and time-consuming. A more cost-effective and efficient alternative is currently offered by AI (Horodyski, 2023). Social media and smartphone technologies have produced large and complex datasets despite the fact that they have brought higher connection opportunities. Contemporary PR practitioners can now utilize AI systems, especially the self-learning ones, to gauge the opinion of the people, manage relationships in real-time, and respond to queries (Simon, 2022).

AI is also incredibly useful in crisis management due to its ability to process probability and work with complex data. One example is AI solutions to assist project managers with risk identification and assessment, and this is essential in effective mitigation of a crisis (Li, Yazdi, Nedjati, Moradi, Adumene, Dao, & Garg, 2024). Artificial intelligence (AI) will support every stage of risk management, involving risk identification, assessment, planning, monitoring, and communication of potential threats by deriving and processing the relevant parametric data (Bah, Faniyan & Farayola, 2025). AI is also capable of analyzing the past schedules of projects to forecast the upcoming timescales. Various teams can use AI to forecast safety, quality, cost, and productivity challenges to intervene in advance. It is important as AI does not only identify hazards, but it also proposes solutions to them, which may be context-specific (Öztemel & Tuncer, 2024).

The complexity and scope of risks have expanded due to the level of global interconnectedness. Quick and accurate crisis preparedness and response are increasingly required (Aladawi & Ahmad, 2023). Predictive AI capabilities allow business organizations to identify crises at an early stage and aid in the early warning systems (Khalifa, Al Baz, & Muttar, 2022). It assists in developing stronger and more comprehensive crisis management strategies by applying it to risk evaluation and anticipatory modeling (Abid & Sulaiman, Chan, Nazir, Abid, Han, & Vega-Muñoz, 2021).

Artificial Intelligence Technologies' Possible Dangers to Public Relations

Artificial intelligence (AI) technology has revolutionized many industries, including public relations (PR), which is both positively and potentially negatively impacted. The ethical argument has gained popularity as AI becomes more prevalent in communication, especially when it comes to privacy violations, the dissemination of false information, automation changes, and other issues

(Saeidnia et al., 2025). One of the most urgent risks associated with AI technologies in the PR sector is the problem of privacy invasion.

When these data find themselves in the possession of cybercriminals, this would be even more problematic. Hackers can determine individuals, decrypt anonymised information, and legally misuse personal data (Tucker, 2019). In addition, the accuracy and performance of AI systems can be compromised by data poisoning caused by the presence of corrupted or unreliable data in AI models (Rumick, 2025). Companies that operate on contaminated information take the risk of experiencing strategic setbacks and severe losses in their public image and brand.

The analysis of the collection, processing, and use of personal data by AI systems is vital for data privacy. Many AI algorithms require large and massive datasets and big data operations within the business or the government. According to Beer (2017), the impact that these systems have had depends on the data created by users, such as cookies. Beer (2017) calls it the social power of algorithms. This raises significant ethical concerns, particularly concerning the area of public relations (Buhmann et al., 2022).

Although AI is bound to be employed in PR, it has critical ethical, professional, and social concerns regarding its development. Among the key issues is that AI will interfere with human-centered decision-making because the technology lacks moral, emotional, and contextual literacy. Moreover, the increasing automation has brought about the issue of job elimination, particularly in communication-related professions.

On the one hand, similar broad acceptance is observed in the further data provided by The State of PR Technology survey, based on which 67.8% of the respondents actively use AI technologies. 61.4% of new users report that they are more productive and efficient. What is more, they can save more time to conduct strategic planning, so 76.6% rely on PR intelligence solutions to automate time-consuming processes. Research and content creation are two more aspects of AI assistance, 42.2% of PR professionals use AI-enabled tools to automate and streamline content of communication, and 58.7% of them use AI to conduct faster research on social media and other platforms (Barryman, 2024).

Despite accounting for automation and job security, a global survey by Sandpiper and PROvoke Media found that 86% of communication specialists viewed AI as an opportunity rather than a threat. According to Davies (2024), 65% of participants believe that the rapid advancement of AI would produce significant changes for public relations professionals worldwide in three years to come. The AI in Communications Industry Opportunities and Risks report, which shows that 86% of participants are confident in generative AI, can corroborate this

viewpoint. The generation gap is obvious: only a quarter of the respondents aged over 45 are worried about job threats, as opposed to half of professionals under the age of 35 (Sandpiper & PROvoke, 2024). Fear of possible displacement exists in only 29 percent of the respondents.

In order to substantiate these results, the 2023 study conducted by the Dfusion Communication agency titled *Is AI Dreaming of Public Relations* demonstrates that some 30 percent of PR executives in their respective industries have already adopted AI technologies, and 69 percent of them hold a positive outlook on the adoption of AI. The rest 41% intend to implement them in the coming years. Though a majority (48) would take the regulation frameworks time, over half (53) would implement it hastily. Most of the participants (93%) consider AI as a useful tool and expect it to enhance media message creation (35%), creative idea generation (48%), and copywriting (75%). Incredibly, 67 percent of respondents believe in funding budgetary increments to support AI adoption and training, and 98 percent of respondents share the notion that PR practitioners are expected to acquire skills associated with AI (Malczewski et al., 2023).

Theoretical Framework: Diffusion of Innovations Theory

This investigation relies on the Diffusion of Innovations Theory put forward by Everett Rogers to explain how newer technology is introduced, understood, and adopted, and integrated into a social or professional system over time. The theory has a high emphasis on the impact of institutional systems, channels of communication, awareness, and perception on the adoption of technology. It defines the key features influencing the choice of people and organizations to embrace innovations: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability.

Since it informs the primary objective of the study, determining how artificial intelligence (AI) is perceived, accepted, and tactically applied in contemporary PR practice, the theory is appropriate in this study. The focus of the study on the patterns of adoption, awareness, and perception of AI influence is in line with the description of the process of innovation-decision presented in the theory. The concept provides a valuable perspective on understanding diversity in adoption within institutional settings through the establishment of AI into a professional communication system that consists of corporate, governmental, consulting, and non-profit organizations.

Also, the Diffusion of Innovations Theory supports the fact that the study is focused on strategic use rather than being exposed to AI technologies. The main aspect of the analysis of AI usage in PR created as a part of the study is that the theory distinguishes between the first realization and actual implementation of an invention in professional life. It also highlights the importance of institutional support and professional leadership in fostering responsible adoption with a

strong focus on the role of such an organization as the Nigerian Institute of Public Relations in supporting professional competence, professional ethics, and AI literacy.

Methodology

A survey research design was employed, whereas convenience sampling and purposive sampling techniques were employed for the data gathering. Because the researchers already had a ready-made database of communication experts, convenience sampling was useful. This was supplemented by purposive sampling, whereby the participants in the database were able to recommend other practitioners who qualified to participate in the study.

The questionnaire was adapted according to the survey requirements of this research based on the respectable academic sources (European Communication Monitor, 2019; Zeffass, Hagelstein, & Tench, 2020). In addition to the demographic questions, it had five significant items that tested the perceived impact of AI on PR. A 5-point Likert Scale ranging from Very unlikely=1, Unlikely=2, Neutral/Undecided=3, Likely=4, and Very likely=5 was used to measure the challenges of applying AI in PR by scoring six propositions.

One hundred communication and public relations professionals filled in the survey. Of this, there were 48 percent females and 52 percent males. The participants had a variety of industries, representing government or public service 35%, and there were several other sectors, which included corporate enterprises (40%), PR firms or consultancies (15%), and non-profit (10%).

Most of the respondents (85) identified general public relations and communication as their primary areas of professional practice. The other major ones included marketing and branding (39%), corporate media relations (35%), online communication (48%), internal communication and change management (55%), and media relations or spokesperson activities (68%).

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data.

Results

The findings are presented based on the research questions

RQ1: How much do Nigerian public relations professionals know about artificial intelligence, and how frequently do they employ AI tools?

The findings demonstrate that the majority of the participants already use AI technologies in one way or another. About 87 percent said they used AI assistants on their mobile phones, and 58 percent of them owned or used smart devices at home or at work.

The use of a chi-square test was to check whether gender played any role in the adoption of AI. It was revealed that there is no meaningful relation between

gender and AI use in mobile devices or smart technologies. There was no difference in the use of AI in relation to gender, therefore (see Table 1).

Table 1: AI and Device Usage

Gender	Using intelligent assistants on your smartphone			Using intelligent gadgets at home or at work		
	Yes	No	Don't know	Yes	No	Don't know
Male	42 (84.0%)	6 (12.0%)	2 (4.0%)	30 (60.0%)	18 (36.0%)	2 (4.0%)
Female	45 (90.0%)	3 (6.0%)	2 (4.0%)	28 (56.0%)	19 (38.0%)	3 (6.0%)
Total	87(87.0%)	9 (9.0%)	4(4.0%)	58 (58.0%)	37 (37.0%)	5 (5.0%)

Source: The researchers' survey, 2026

The above table represents the use of AI assistants and devices among one hundred specialists in communication and public relations, divided by gender. The smartphone assistants were used by 84% of the men, and 60% of the men said they used intelligent devices at home or at the place of work. In females, 90% were using smartphone assistants and 56% smart devices.

The presence of a statistically significant relationship between AI adoption and gender was determined using the chi-square test. Gender did not significantly affect the use of smart gadgets ($\chi^2 (N = 100) = 0.714, p = 0.700$) or intelligent assistants ($\chi^2 (N = 100) = 1.213, p = 0.546$).

Table 2: Public Relations and Communication Experts' Views about AI Respondents' descriptions of AI

Respondents' descriptions of AI	The percentage (%) of respondents' descriptions of AI
Intelligent programs (automated decision-making)	78.4%
Acquiring knowledge and becoming better through learning by means of data	52.1%.
Activities that are directly assisted by human resources	65.2%
Adapting to new goals and unforeseen fieldwork	45.7%
Making sense and acting upon human language	50.3%
Recognizing human emotions	30.5%
Sharing all human mental capacities	18.9%
Having emotions, as humans do	20.2%

Source: The researchers' survey, 2026

RQ2: Perceived Influence of AI on Public Relations and Communication Management

Artificial intelligence is expected to have a significant impact on the communication and public relations fields in Nigeria. The participants stated that AI is highly likely to:

- Repackage the broader PR and communication landscape (Mean = 3.67, SD = 1.09),
- Modify their organizations' internal processes (Mean = 3.54, SD = 1.12),
- Modify their daily communication activities and employment (Mean = 3.59, SD = 1.20).

These reflections demonstrate that although there is some partial misunderstanding of AI, Nigerian professionals recognize that it is becoming more prominent and changing the way an organization works and the personal duties of individuals.

Table 3: Perceived Impact of AI on PR and Communication Functions

Source: The researchers' survey, 2026

AI expected influence	Mean (M) Standard Deviation (SD)	Mean (M) Standard Deviation (SD)
The public relations and communications industry	3.74	1.10
My organization's or unit's operational procedures	3.56	1.14
My own work style and day-to-day professional duties	3.63	1.18

Thus: Professionals were asked to rate the potential influence of AI on various facets of their work given the increasing incorporation of AI technologies like virtual voice assistants (like Siri and Alexa) and algorithms utilized in digital media platforms. A 5-point Likert scale was used to score the responses (1 = Very low impact, 5 = Very high impact).

RQ3: Challenges in Adopting AI in Public Relations and Communication

One of the core objectives of the given research was to determine the obstacles that practitioners view in integrating AI into communication and PR work. The one-sample test results indicate that the vast majority of professionals do not believe that the adoption of AI is that complicated. Even though the respondents recognize the disruptive potential of AI in all industries, they do not foresee critical obstacles in the processes of acquiring or developing the relevant enablers to use it. The central prerequisites to successful AI integration including creating relevant skills and competence (74.8%), the willingness and motivation of employees (79.1%), organizational preparedness and infrastructures (64.5%), management and leadership support (70.8%), national and social infrastructures (59.4%), and acceptance by the end-users (69.7) were perceived to be feasible as a rule (see Table 4). Such a positive attitude demonstrates a growing acknowledgment that AI is no longer a far-off invention but a technology that is already affecting the communication process and professional demands.

RQ4: Difficulties in Including AI in Public Relations Procedures

The t -test also indicated that the practitioners were not overwhelmingly worried about AI threatening their jobs or their identity as a professional. Most people did not agree that AI would threaten their employment (71.8%), lower their wages (72.1%), disrupt the competency levels of the staff (68.2%), erode job ownership (69.7%), decrease the essential skills (78.4%), or de-professionalise (79.1%) (see Table 5). Such findings indicate that professionals have a strong

belief that they will remain relevant despite the development of AI technologies. The mean scores are rather low and do not coincide with the benchmark value, which is 4, which means a sufficiently low level of perceived risk.

Table 4: Perceived Obstacles to AI Adoption in Communication and Public Relations

Factors Affecting Adoption of AI	Communication Roles'	M	SD	T-Value	P-Value
Proficiency in AI use by PR/communication professionals		2.72	1.08	-18.413	0.000
Adoption of AI by PR/communication personnel		2.66	1.10	-19.275	0.000
Internal infrastructure, such as budget and technology		2.84	1.14	-14.601	0.000
Support from clients and leadership		2.80	1.12	-15.728	0.000
National infrastructure (such as laws and fast internet)		3.12	1.21	-11.482	0.000
Acceptance by external stakeholders and users		2.89	1.03	-15.924	0.000

Source: The researchers' survey 2026

Using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Not tough, 5 = Very difficult), participants assessed how difficult it was to meet different AI deployment requirements. A high degree of perceived difficulty is indicated by the test value of 4.

RQ4: Perceived Risks of Integrating AI into Public Relations and Communication

Another one-sample t-test revealed that practitioners do not tend to think that AI poses significant threats to their work, economic security, and professional integrity. There was considerable disagreement among the respondents that Job security (72.6%), salary levels (72.8%), workforce competency (68.3%), task clarity (70.9%), critical competences (79.3%), or professional identity (79.7) would all be lost as a result of AI. These findings (refer to Table 5) show that most communication professionals have a lot of confidence to continue being valuable and adjusting to the changes, despite the increasing use of AI in their workflow. The poor mean scores in comparison to the reference point in 4 represent the weak perception of risk.

Table 5: Perceived Risk of AI in Communication Management and Public Relation

Area of Risk Perception	M	SD	t-test	p-value
Professionals in communication will lose their jobs	2.48	1.19	-19.210	0.000
Professionals in communication will see pay reductions	2.53	1.17	-18.342	0.000
Employee competency will suffer	2.75	1.14	-15.108	0.000
Roles and responsibilities will become ambiguous	2.60	1.22	-16.489	0.000
The profession will lose essential core competencies	2.18	1.21	-21.804	0.000
The occupation will become less unique	2.10	1.25	-22.716	0.000

Source: The researchers' survey, 2026

Note: Each danger was scored by respondents using a 5-point Likert scale, with 1 denoting "not likely" and 5 denoting "very likely." A high perceived risk is indicated by the test value of 4.

Discussion and Conclusion

Despite the fact that a significant amount of the research is theoretical rather than empirical, academics have widely acknowledged the impact of artificial intelligence on the domains of communication and public relations. Few studies have examined real-world work experiences; instead, they have primarily focused on awareness, skill needs, and the challenges of adopting AI. Even when research participants showed a basic awareness and grasp of AI, the consistently low mean scores, especially when it comes to perceived risks and barriers, suggest that practitioners might not fully understand the wider implications of AI for their area.

The results are at odds with previous research, including Zerfass et al. (2020) and CIPR (2021). For instance, Zerfass et al. found that organizational infrastructure (M = 3.54, SD = 1.15) and professional competencies (M = 3.58, SD = 1.04) are major obstacles to the use of AI in communication work. However, these areas seemed less concerning in our investigation, having correspondingly lower mean values of 2.84 (SD = 1.14) and 2.18 (SD = 1.21). Perceptions of the risks associated with AI also varied significantly from earlier studies. AI is still a relatively new concept in academic discussions and PR practice in Nigeria. Senior practitioners acknowledged awareness of AI but

reported little interaction with its more profound ramifications, in part because its impact is not yet fully apparent in the local industry.

These findings highlight how crucial it is for public relations and communication professionals to have greater knowledge about AI technologies. There is an evident conflict between the use of AI technology and the comprehension of its strategic and ethical implications. To close this gap, practitioners must actively update their knowledge and develop skills relevant to an AI-driven communication environment.

Even if AI technologies are very helpful for communication practice, mastering them professionally is not the same as using them on a daily basis. While Zerfass et al. (2020, p. 386) warn that "learning by doing" can only go so far, Galloway and Swiatek (2018, p.734) emphasize the need to gain basic knowledge about AI without necessarily becoming technical experts. AI allows practitioners to become "masters of the data," even though technology cannot replace human traits like empathy and emotional intelligence (Zerfass et al., 2020, p. 386).

AI education shouldn't be limited to practitioners. Students preparing for careers in public relations and communication must also be exposed to AI principles and techniques. Consequently, it is the responsibility of educators to include AI in their lessons. To do this successfully, lecturers themselves need to continuously update their knowledge, either through professional training or particular certification programs.

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Abiodun Adesina initiated the idea of this paper, coordinated the data gathering, and Greg Ezeah proofread and reworked the paper after the reviewers' corrections.

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There is no conflict of interest with any sources or persons from the beginning of this paper to the end of it.

Ethical clearance

The authors kindly sought and duly got ethical clearance from the respondents and or every other relevant authority who provided the data or information used for this paper.

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